

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF FUEL POLLUTION ON THE WEAR OF AUTOMOTIVE ENGINE PARTS

Abdusamatov F.

Assistant of "Automotive" Faculty in Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Abstract

Questions about the close relationship between the quality of fuel and the design of automobile engines are considered. The results of a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the influence of fuel contamination on the durability and wear of automotive engine parts are presented.

Keywords: Car engine, contaminated fuel, atmospheric dust, abrasive wear, durability, fuel cleaning.

One of the most important characteristics of modern internal combustion engines is their reliability, which makes it possible to quantify the change in engine quality over the time of its operation. Such an assessment greatly facilitates the development of comprehensive measures for the further improvement of existing and the creation of new engine designs, and contributes to an increase in the efficiency of their operation.

Over the past decade, a significant increase in the reliability of motor vehicles has been achieved, which is due to a significant increase in the quality of structural and fuel-lubricating materials (FCM) [5, 6, 7].

There is a complex relationship between the FCM, the engine and its operation [5,6], therefore, for organizations that produce and operate internal combustion engines (ICE) it is necessary to know the FCM chemotology: operating conditions and processes of its qualitative and quantitative changes in the engine; identification of patterns that link the quality of FCM with operational and environmental reliability, as well as engine efficiency; establishing optimal requirements for the quality of FCM and determining the conditions for its rational use, etc.

Improving the quality and rational use of fuel is one of the main measures to improve the efficiency of the use of automobile engines. Thus, a significant increase in the reliability of the fuel equipment (FA) and the engine itself, achieved over the past twenty years, has largely contributed to the improvement in fuel quality [1,6]. This is due to the fact that fuel is one of the main functional elements of the engine, which largely determines its reliability, environmental safety and efficiency.

Fuel quality and engine design are interrelated, so improving fuel quality and engine reliability must be considered in close relationship with each other. This formulation of the problem allows not only to increase the durability of engines, but also is the basis for their further improvement, improving their environmental performance and reducing fuel consumption.

One of the main characteristics that determine the quality of automotive fuels is the purity of the fuel, i.e. the absence of various contaminants in it. Upon entering the engine, contaminated fuel causes intense wear of the mated friction pairs, which leads to a decrease in the reliability and durability of both the engine and the vehicle as a whole. The practical experience of motor building shows that it is possible to achieve high durability of motors only by reducing the abrasive wear of autotractor engine parts.[1,3]

The reliability of this hypothesis is confirmed by the results of experiments by a number of researchers [1,3,4,5]. It has been established that in modern automobile engines more than half of the wear is caused by abrasive particles, while this type of wear of engine parts is predominant for vehicles operating in various zones of Central Asia. This circumstance indicates that the main reserve for increasing the durability of engines is to reduce the abrasive component of wear by protecting engines from dust particles, improving air, fuel and oil filters, as well as all places where dust can enter the engine. From the foregoing, it follows that reducing the wear of engine parts of vehicles operating in hot climatic and dusty conditions of Central Asia from abrasive wear is of paramount importance.

Of particular importance from the point of view of abrasive wear is the dustiness of the air, especially in the summer, dry period of the year. The air dust content in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the summer is on average 1.5-2.0 g/m³, and often during strong winds -17 g/m³. For clarity, it is enough to say that with air dust content of 0.8... 2 g/m³ visibility is completely lost. Obviously, the operation of machines in such extreme conditions has its own characteristics and increasing their wear resistance and durability requires a specific and original approach to solving the issue.

Thus, the main amount of fuel and air contaminants is atmospheric dust, which causes abrasive wear of parts and failure of the engine power system.

Therefore, the fuel entering the engine must be purified from various contaminants and, above all, from dust particles that cause abrasive wear of parts of the engine cylinder-piston group. In this regard, the fuel is cleaned during production, during bottling and storage at storage bases, during distribution and on the engine itself.

Modern car engines year after year are becoming more demanding on the purity of the fuel, in addition, environmental requirements for them are also becoming tougher. Therefore, according to the manufacturer's data, oil refineries (refineries) of the Republic of Uzbekistan produce a quality product. However, fuel often gets contaminated into the tanks of cars, although when the cause of such a problem was identified, it turned out that the tanks for storing and transporting fuel were poorly cleaned or not cleaned at all. At the bottom of the tanks, mechanical impurities and water accumulate, which, getting into the fuel, lead to a reduction in the service life of the filters, and subsequently to the failure of the engine itself, i.e. engine operation on such fuel leads to corrosion, accelerated wear, power loss, etc.

[3,7]. And, this phenomenon is clearly expressed in hot-climatic and dusty operating conditions of autotractor engines, i.e. in the regional zones of Central Asia [5], in particular in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, we carried out work to identify the dependence of the wear of automotive engine parts on fuel pollution and dustiness of atmospheric air.

It has been established that the amount of contaminants in autotractor tanks is directly dependent on the dustiness of the area and the season of operation of the vehicle and ranges from a few grams to 300-500 g/t of fuel. In some cases, up to 8–10 g of contaminants were removed from the coarse fuel filter of a car operating in dusty regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in 1 liter of fuel [2,4].

It was revealed that the main amount of contaminants in the fuel of cars is atmospheric dust, which causes abrasive wear of parts and failure of the HE. Due to the fact that the magnitude of this type of wear is determined by the abrasive ability of dust, it is of particular interest from the point of view of developing measures to improve the wear resistance of parts to identify the abrasive properties of fuel contaminants and atmospheric (soil) dust.

The abrasive ability of dust depends primarily on its dispersed and mineralogical compositions, therefore, of theoretical and practical interest is the quantitative assessment of the abrasive ability of road dust, natural fuel pollutants and artificially quartz pollutant used in testing fuel, oil and air filters.

To determine the distribution of the disperse composition and wear capacity, road dust from the surfaces of the hood, cab, and wings was studied, and deposits from the fuel filters of cars operating in various regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used as fuel contaminants [2,4].

The results of the study showed that the distribution of atmospheric dust particles, as well as liquid pollution, can be uniquely determined by the least squares method using the following equation [4]:

$$\operatorname{tg} \beta = 0,4426 - 0,1647 \lg x_0$$

It follows from this equation that the distribution of atmospheric dust particles, as well as liquid pollution, can be unambiguously determined by the value of $\lg x_0$ or x_0 , which provides a basis for classifying the dispersed compositions of various dusts and allows

them to be compared, and also greatly facilitates the development of theoretical issues of abrasive wear. In this regard, experimental studies were carried out to determine the wear capacity of fuel contaminants [1,2,4]. The results of these studies showed that with an increase in the content of quartz in natural road dusts, their abrasive ability increases. Deposits from fuel filters have a somewhat lower abrasive capacity compared to road dust from the same areas, which, apparently, is due to a change in the dispersed and mineralogical composition of sediments. All natural pollutants are 1.7-4 times less abrasive than the artificial quartz pollutant.

To determine the dependence of the abrasive ability of the same mass of dust on the particle size, artificial and natural road dusts were tested, separated by precipitation into the following particle size groups: 0–4; 4–7; 7–10; 10–20; 20–40; 40–63; 63–80; 80–100 μm .

The abrasive ability of artificial quartz dust and natural road dust (Fig. 1) reaches its maximum value, respectively, at particle sizes of about 70 and 55 microns.

The abrasive properties of dust begin to increase rapidly as soon as the particle size becomes larger than the thickness of the oil film.

From particle sizes of quartz dust on average more than 80 microns and road dust on average more than 60 microns, their abrasive ability gradually begins to decrease. This is due to both a decrease in the possibility of large particles getting into the gap between friction pairs, and a decrease in the stress that destroys them [4].

The results of calculating the abrasive ability of dusts (dashed curves in Fig. 1), depending on the size of their grains, are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental data (solid curves). The calculations were carried out with the following parameter values: for quartz dust $\sigma = 105.2 \mu\text{m}$; $m = 0.6$; for natural road dust - $\sigma = 72.3 \mu\text{m}$; $m = 0.6$ [4].

The abrasive ability of dusts depends linearly on the amount of quartz in it (straight line 3 in Fig. 1), so it can be assumed that quartz is the main component that determines their abrasive qualities. Therefore, in order to reduce the wear of parts of the cylinder-piston group of automobile engines, it is necessary to properly clean the fuel and air entering the engine.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the abrasive ability of dust particles of the same mass (A) on the size (X) of particles (1 - natural road dust, 2 - artificial quartz dust) and on the content of quartz in the dust (3) (σ -standard deviation; m -proportionality factor).

CONCLUSIONS: one of the main characteristics that determine the quality of automotive fuels is the purity of the fuel, i.e. the absence of various contaminants in it.

- the main amount of contaminants in the fuels of vehicles operating in hot climatic conditions is atmospheric dust, which causes abrasive wear of parts and failure of fuel equipment;

- with an increase in the content of quartz in natural dusts, their abrasive ability increases.

- to reduce the wear of the parts of the cylinder-piston group of automobile engines, it is necessary to properly clean the fuel and air entering the engine.

References

1. Каримходжаев Н., Эркинов И. Б. У. Влияние чистоты топлива на техническо-экономическую эффективность автомобиля // Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 5-3 (86). – С. 9-12.

2. Каримходжаев Н., Косимов И.С., Ёкубов Ё.О. Оценка абразивной агрессивности загрязнений топлива автомобильных двигателей, эксплуатирующийся в жаркой, высоко запыленной зоне Центральной Азии // Универсум: Технические науки: электрон. научн. журн. 2019. № 11(68). URL: <http://7universum.com/ru/tech/archive/item/8242>

3. Каюмов Б.А. Обеспечение надежности системы питания современных бензиновых двигателей в условиях жаркого климата.-Андижан, Андижонашриёт –манбаа.2019.-104с.

4. Крамаренко Г.В., Салимов А.У., Каримходжаев Н. Качество топлива и надежность автотракторных двигателей. –Ташкент: Фан, 1992.-126с.

5. Надежность технических систем. Справочник Беляев Ю. К., Богатырев В. А., Болотин В. В. и др. Под ред. Ушакова И. А. М.: Радио и связь. 1985. 608 с.

6. Николаенко А. В. Теория, конструкция и расчет автотракторных двигателей. М.: Колос. 1984. 335 с.

7. Эксплуатация ДВС в условиях стран Азии, Африки и Латинской Америки.

Основы климатической приспособленности ДВС. – Киев: УМК ВО, 1988.-285с. 8. Recommendations for Cleaning and Pretreatment of Heavy Fuel Oil Alfa Laval. London. 2012. -124 p.

9. Фильтры / Чистим топливо //filtr%20%20NAMI.pdf.

10. Numanov M. et al. АНАЛИЗ ФРАКЦИОННОГО КОЛИЧЕСТВА БЕНЗИНА //Главный редактор: Ахметов Сайранбек Махсатович, д-р техн. наук; Заместитель главного редактора: Ахмеднабиев Расул Магомедович, канд. техн. наук; Члены редакционной коллегии. – 2021. – С. 20.

ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO THE MANAGEMENT OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF MILITARY EQUIPMENT AND WAYS TO IMPROVE THEM

Baranov Yu.

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, Professor of the Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Baranov A.

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, associate professor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Kyrylchuk V.

Senior instructor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Kovalchuk S.

Instructor, Department of Combat (Operational) Support Units Tactics, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Ivanskyi V.

Associate professor, Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of military equipment (ME) in the process of its operation. The article analyzes the existing approaches to the management of TC of ME in the process of its operation, taking into account the experience of the Joint Forces Operation (JFO).

Keywords: military equipment; technical condition; maintenance; combat operations; mathematical model.